

Table name: Data abstraction form for *The views, perspectives, and experiences of academic researchers with data sharing and reuse: a meta-synthesis*

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Data dictionary is for the following files:

- 1) DataSharing_StudyCharacteristics.csv
- 2) DataSharing_ParticipantCharacteristics.csv
- 3) DataSharing_Outcomes.csv
- 4) DataSharing_CASP.csv

File: Study Characteristics			
Column Name	Optional	Format	Description
RefID	No	Text	Definition: RefID is short for reference identification The format is as follows: AuthorLastName PublicationYear <i>Example: Smith 2010</i>
First Author	No	Text	Last name of the first author on the article
Year of Publication	No	Text	Year the article was published Year is listed only, not the day or month
Article Title	No	Text	Title as it is listed on the article
Journal Name ^a	Yes	Text	Name of the journal the article is published in
Conference Name/Book/Gray Literature ^a	Yes	Text	Name of the conference or book or gray literature source the article is from
Study Design 01	Yes	Text	Type of study reported in the article
Study Design 02	Yes	Text	Type of study reported in the article if more than one qualitative study conducted and reported
Study Period	No	Text	The time period when the study was conducted May include month or season (e.g., summer 2011)
Study Purpose / Objective / Research Questions	No	Text	The purpose (objective or research questions) of the study as described by the authors The aim of the study is also acceptable
Principal Experiences Explored	No	Text	The principal experiences explored as described by the author
Geographical Location	No	Text	The geographical location of where the study was conducted. Must include country. This is NOT the location of home institution of author(s).
Setting	No	Text	Where the study took place

Associated Discipline	No	Text	Branch of learning or knowledge, area of academia, or field of study
Qualitative Methodologic Orientation	No	Text	The methodologic orientation as reported by the author
Theoretical Framework	No	Text	The theoretical framework as reported by the author
Comments	Yes	Text	Any notes relevant to the article abstracted.
<i>^a 1) Each article must list either a Journal Name or a Conference Name; 2) Books, dissertations, and gray literature is listed under Conference Name</i>			
File: Participants Characteristics			
Column Name	Optional	Format	Description
RefID	No	Text	Definition: RefID is short for reference identification The format is as follows: AuthorLastName PublicationYear <i>Example: Smith 2010</i>
Sample Size (Total) [Study Design 01]	Yes	Text	Number of participants recruited into the study (human subjects)
Sample Size (Completed) [Study Design 01]	Yes	Text	Number of participants that completed the study (human subjects)
Number of Participants by Sex [Study Design 01]	Yes	Text	Number of participants that completed the study reported by sex (human subjects)
Participant Characteristics [Study Design 01]	Yes	Text	Characteristics of participants that completed the study (human subjects) For example: this could include age, employment status, education status, etc.
Sample Size (Total) [Study Design 02]	Yes	Text	Number of participants recruited into the study (human subjects)
Sample Size (Completed) [Study Design 02]	Yes	Text	Number of participants that completed the study (human subjects)
Number of Participants by Sex [Study Design 02]	Yes	Text	Number of participants that completed the study reported by sex (human subjects)
Participant Characteristics [Study Design 02]	Yes	Text	Characteristics of participants that completed the study (human subjects) For example: this could include age, employment status, education status, etc.
File: Outcomes			
Column Name	Optional	Format	Description
RefID	No	Text	Definition: RefID is short for reference identification The format is as follows: AuthorLastName

			PublicationYear <i>Example: Smith 2010</i>
Direct Participant Quotation ^b	Yes	Text	Direct participant quotations
Primary Author's Analysis ^b	Yes	Text	Primary author's interpretation of participant responses
^b These 2 columns are repeated for studies which report multiple direct participant quotations and primary author's analysis			
File: CASP			
Column Name	Optional	Format	Description The following was considered in answering the questions
Was there a clear statement of the aims of the research?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What was the goal of the research • Why it was thought important • Its relevance
Is a qualitative methodology appropriate?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the research seeks to interpret or illuminate the actions and/or subjective experiences of research participants • Is qualitative research the right methodology for addressing the research goal
Was the research design appropriate to address the aims of the research?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the researcher has justified the research design (e.g., have they discussed how they decided which method to use)
Was the recruitment strategy appropriate to the aims of the research?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the researcher has explained how the participants were selected • If they explained why the participants they selected were the most appropriate to provide access to the type of knowledge sought by the study • If there are any discussions around recruitment (e.g. why some people chose not to take part)
Was the data collected in a way that addressed the research issue?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the setting for the data collection was justified • If it is clear how data were collected (e.g. focus group, semi-structured interview, etc.) • If the researcher has justified the methods chosen • If the researcher has made the methods explicit (e.g. for interview method, is there an indication of how interviews are conducted, or did they use a topic guide) • If methods were modified during the study. If so, has the researcher explained how and why • If the form of data is clear (e.g., tape recordings, video material, notes etc.) • If the researcher has discussed saturation of data

Has the relationship between researcher and participants been adequately considered?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the researcher critically examined their own role, potential bias and influence during (a) formulation of the research questions (b) data collection, including sample recruitment and choice of location • How the researcher responded to events during the study and whether they considered the implications of any changes in the research design
Have ethical issues been taken into consideration?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there are sufficient details of how the research was explained to participants for the reader to assess whether ethical standards were maintained • If the researcher has discussed issues raised by the study (e.g. issues around informed consent or confidentiality or how they have handled the effects of the study on the participants during and after the study) • If approval has been sought from the ethics committee
Was the data analysis sufficiently rigorous?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there is an in-depth description of the analysis process • If thematic analysis is used. If so, is it clear how the categories/themes were derived from the data • Whether the researcher explains how the data presented were selected from the original sample to demonstrate the analysis process • If sufficient data are presented to support the findings • To what extent contradictory data are taken into account • Whether the researcher critically examined their own role, potential bias and influence during analysis and selection of data for presentation
Is there a clear statement of findings?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the findings are explicit • If there is adequate discussion of the evidence both for and against the researcher's arguments • If the researcher has discussed the credibility of their findings (e.g., triangulation, respondent validation, more than one analyst) • If the findings are discussed in relation to the original research question
How valuable is the research?	No	Text	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the researcher discusses the contribution the study makes to existing knowledge or understanding (e.g., do they consider the

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			<p>findings in relation to current practice or policy, or relevant research based literature</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If they identify new areas where research is necessary • If the researchers have discussed whether or how the findings can be transferred to other populations or considered other ways the research may be used
Comments	Yes	Text	Any relevant notes were recorded